

ISic1642

I.Sicily inscription 1642

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14605

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Clari]ssimae memoriae vir[---]
2. [pro]vinciarum [---]
3. [---]fidelis [---]
4. [---]NTA[---]

Apparatus

Text after Orsi 1895

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 494041

EDCS 12700070

Bibliography

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